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In the Spirit of Leadership: The Chronicles of Female Student Leaders

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Abstract

This phenomenology study aimed to explore and understand the lived experiences of a female student leaders. Using purposive sampling, the participating 14 female student leaders from different public schools were identified. All of them are participated in the in-depth interviews. Results revealed the experiences of the participants: encountering challenges in managing the behavior of the students, experiencing self-doubt as student leader, struggling with balancing responsibilities as a student and student-leader, engendering sense of pride to take on the role of a student-leader, and navigating different perspectives as a student-leader creates uncertainty. In response to the challenges they have encountered, they deemed the following coping strategies essential: nurturing patience while dealing challenges in a leadership role, seeking support and guidance in overcoming responsibilities, managing academic performance alongside leadership duties, and choosing words carefully to prevent causing offense of others. Upon reflecting on their entire experience, they arrived at the following insights: demonstrate complete accounting in leadership duties, exude strength and confidence, enhanced leadership and communication skills, demonstrate fervent passion and commitment in leadership, and empowerment and breaking of gender stereotypes in leadership. The results of this study were anticipated to be meaningful and important to the participants, teachers, students, and researchers.

Keywords: *experience, female student leaders, phenomenology approach, qualitative, Philippines*

Introduction

In spite of significant strides in promoting gender equality in today's society, women still grapple with self-doubt and tend to perceive their own performance and leadership abilities less positively than men. This disparity poses hurdles for female leadership within workplaces, impeding their progression toward and retention of senior leadership roles. Numerous challenges contribute to this, including discrimination, subconscious biases affecting judgment, lower expectations compared to their male counterparts, and the unfortunate tendency to take women less seriously as leaders. Moreover, women in leadership roles often encounter barriers like second-generation gender bias, where systemic norms hinder their advancement, the natural inclination of individuals to support those resembling themselves, and the lack of preparedness in companies to place women in top-tier positions. These multifaceted challenges significantly impact the trajectory of women aiming for leadership positions (Botwin, 2022).

In Quebec, the issue of women's leadership faces a complex landscape shaped by diverse biases and barriers. Despite being part of Canada, women in Quebec, like elsewhere in the country, grapple with significant underrepresentation in both political and professional leadership spheres. These disparities stem from compounded discrimination, including racism, colonialism, ableism, and homophobia. A recent Quebec survey highlighted stark differences between men and women in leadership positions, with nearly half of respondents noting a clear lack of fairness in internal promotions. Additionally, unconscious gender bias emerges as a major hurdle preventing women from ascending to leadership roles, with almost two-thirds of employed women attributing the scarcity of female executives to gender discrimination. This multifaceted scenario underscores the profound challenges obstructing women's advancement in leadership roles in Quebec (Spiridon, 2020).

In the Philippines, the underrepresentation of women in leadership roles remains a pressing concern. Women's engagement in the labor force is notably limited, contributing to a prominent gender gap within the workforce. Despite the existence of the Philippine Magna Carta for Women, designed to eradicate discrimination, obstacles persist, hindering women's economic empowerment. Additionally, the prevalence of violence against women is alarmingly high, with one in every four Filipino women enduring gender-based violence. This collective situation underscores the multifaceted challenges impeding women's progress towards equality and leadership in the Philippines (Del Monte, 2022).

In the increasingly diverse and interconnected world, despite strides made in gender equality, a significant gap persists in offering leadership opportunities to female students. This gap is rooted in systemic barriers that impede women's progress into leadership roles, especially within educational settings. This study is driven by the need to uncover, acknowledge, and comprehend the varied experiences of female student leaders. Its purpose extends beyond mere exploration; it aims to amplify their voices, shedding light on their challenges while providing a platform for their innovative ideas. Moreover, this research endeavors to serve as a blueprint, urging educational stakeholders to develop targeted programs and initiatives aimed at supporting and nurturing the leadership potential of these young women.

In alignment with this pursuit, numerous research endeavors have explored student leadership. Notable among these is Liu et al.'s (2019) investigation titled "Leader Development Begins at Home: Overparenting Harms Adolescent Leader Emergence," which delves into the impact of parental influence on young leaders. Additionally, Hou et al.'s (2019) work, "Impact of Instructional Leadership on High School Student Academic Achievement in China," contributes insights into the relationship between leadership within educational

contexts and student achievement. Meanwhile, this study distinguishes itself by focusing squarely on the experiences of female student leaders, encompassing a comprehensive examination of both their triumphs and the multifaceted challenges they confront in their leadership journeys.

Research Questions

The purpose of this phenomenological study was to gain a deeper understanding of the lived experiences, perspectives, and challenges of female students in leadership roles in public schools in the Davao region. Specifically, this study aimed to uncover the unique essence of a female student in their leadership experiences, shedding light on their motivations, leadership styles, and the impact they had on their peers, schools, and communities. The study aimed to develop and gather deep and authentic information through qualitative methods such as in-depth interviews (IDI). This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What were the experiences of female student leaders faced in their leadership roles?
2. How did female student leaders cope with the challenges as they navigated their leadership roles?
3. What were the insights of female student leaders that they could share to inspire and empower other young women to pursue leadership roles?

Methodology

Research Design

This study was utilized a qualitative research design specifically employing a phenomenological approach. According to Bhandari (2023), the qualitative research design is a collection and analysis of non-numerical data for a comprehensive understanding of the thoughts, ideas, and experiences of the participants. Through this design, researchers can gather in-depth insights into the phenomenon or generate new ideas for the study, based on the experiences of the participants involved.

In the context of the study, qualitative research design was used because it is the ideal method for exploring less explored research topics. This allowed for a deep understanding of the experiences of female student leaders. All data was gathered through one-on-one conversations called in-depth interviews.

Furthermore, a phenomenological approach was utilized in the study which focused on the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of the participants involved in the phenomena. This kind of approach in qualitative research design uncovers how participants experienced the event through an act of collecting deep information and perceptions such as interviews, and discussions. The collected data was carefully analyzed and organized in connection with related phrases and themes which gives an in-depth understanding of the topic being studied (Creswell, 2013).

In the study, phenomenology aimed to investigate the experiences, motivation, challenges, and the impact of female student leaders on their peers and communities. This approach was well-suited to the topic, as it aimed to explore the lived experiences of the participants concerning the phenomenon.

Participants

In this study, it utilized a qualitative-phenomenological research approach. The process of selecting participants was deliberate, with a focused on ensuring the inclusion of individuals representing diverse age groups, genders, socio-economic backgrounds, and ethnicities. Consequently, no eligible participants faced exclusion based on these demographic factors. Moreover, a core principle of the study was the equitable treatment of all participants, ensuring that they were equally exposed to potential risks and benefits associated with their involvement in the research.

Furthermore, within the scope of this phenomenological investigation, the participants were drawn from the Municipality of Kapalong. Under the established inclusion criteria, the most suitable participants should exhibit the following attributes: (1) they must be a female student leaders enrolled in elementary school; (2) they must held a leadership position for a school year; and (3) they must currently serving leadership role within their school situated in the Municipality of Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Moreover, the selected participants should also express a readiness to actively engage in the study's processes.

Additionally, there were a total of 14 individuals involved in this study. These fourteen participants were engaged in detailed one-on-one interviews. The participants were carefully chosen and designated to play an active role in this qualitative research endeavor. This count, with a minimum of fourteen individuals for the in-depth interviews, should prove adequate in reaching a saturation point, at which point recurring themes are identified (Mason 2010).

Procedure

As a researcher, the researcher followed a rigorous process to gather data and other essential information for the study. Before beginning the study, the researcher consulted with the advisor to develop a plan and identify the necessary steps for completion. This allowed the researcher to start the study with a clear understanding of the goals and objectives, as well as the methods and procedures to be used.

To ensure accurate data collection and facilitate smooth analysis and interpretation, the researcher established contact with the fourteen

female students identified for the study and confirmed their availability. Since the participants were from different public schools, the researcher informed them about the research and clearly communicated its purpose and goals.

Before the actual interviews, the researcher informed the participants about the purpose of the study. In this qualitative research study, interviews were the primary method employed for data collection. As described by Smith et al. (2013), these qualitative data-gathering approaches aimed to provide valuable insights into the underlying processes and changes in individuals' perspectives. The researcher ensured that there was a clear understanding of the study's nature and purpose before introducing it to the participants and seeking their consent.

Ensuring the trustworthiness of results is a crucial aspect of conducting high-quality qualitative research. One technique recommended for assessing the credibility of findings is member checking, also referred to as participant or respondent validation. Member checking involves the process of sharing collected data or research findings with participants to verify their accuracy and alignment with their own experiences. This technique is often listed as one of several validation approaches in qualitative research (Birt et al., 2016).

Furthermore, the ethical soundness and trustworthiness of the study's findings, the researcher submitted the manuscript to the research technical panel for a thorough evaluation. After receiving approval from all panel members, the researcher wrote a permission letter to the institution where it plans to conduct the study. And then used this letter to request authorization from the appropriate institution.

Data Analysis

The data that was gathered in the research was presented and examined in the study depending on the research's objectives or goals. This necessitates a thorough examination of the content of the participant's responses to arrive at the study's conclusions. As a result, the goal of data analysis was to look for common patterns that could provide ideas that could answer the research questions posed in this study.

Moreover, the data collected in the study was systematically organized and stored by the researcher using technical resources. The audio and video recorders were utilized to capture the conversation. Working, organizing, and combining material into manageable pieces; synthesizing, searching for patterns, and discussing what is significant and what is to be learned are all part of qualitative analysis. The researcher conducted a qualitative content analysis to provide a more thorough analysis of the study. Content analysis involves the study of making inferences from a text to other states or qualities of the source using a repeatable and precise procedure. Following the research analysis, all examined information was derived from a genuine source, which were the informants.

Thematic analysis was used in this study to analyze the collected and acquired data. During the data-gathering phase, the goal was to find any patterns that represent concepts that the participants represent. The information was then sorted into logical categories that summarize and make sense of the note's manuscript. Thematic analysis is a flexible qualitative analytical method that allows the researcher to derive new ideas and concepts from data.

Moreover, thematic analysis is a good research approach when trying to find out something about people's views, opinions, knowledge, experiences, or values from a set of qualitative data such as interview transcripts, social media profiles, or survey responses. Thematic analysis was adaptable, and what researchers do with the themes once they have been discovered varies depending on the research goals and the analysis process. Many academics utilize theme analysis to come closer to their data and have a better understanding of the content.

Furthermore, the researcher completed the procedures of familiarizing the data, producing initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and identifying themes, and constructing the report. The analytical procedure began with transcription. Separate it into bits or elements by analyzing it. It is a process in which the researcher attempts to make sense of the data he or she has gathered.

Finally, the researcher listened to the recorded interviews of the participants and transcribed them to facilitate the coding process later on. Then reviewed the data multiple times to familiarize myself with the responses and quickly identify the most common ones. The researcher aggregated these common responses and derived a few themes, which were further refined to a select few. Data reduction techniques were employed to eliminate irrelevant data and repurpose it as valuable study material for readers to understand. A substantial amount of qualitative data was sorted and organized, enabling the researcher to integrate and categorize it efficiently. Data display techniques were utilized to present the data in matrices, charts, and graphs, allowing readers to draw their conclusions.

Ethical Considerations

When gathering data from individuals, scientists and researchers must always abide by a set of ethical principles that serve as a guide for research designs and procedures. Understanding real-world occurrences, researching potent therapies, examining behavior, and enhancing lives in other ways are frequently the objectives of human research. Ethical guidelines must be observed when doing research. These factors function to uphold academic or scientific integrity, increase the validity of the research, and protect the rights of research participants (Bhandari, 2022).

Respect for Persons is the researcher's obligation to exploit the weaknesses of the research participants. Voluntary participation of the participants is respected and appreciated thus; I did not force the participants to participate in the study. Self-sufficiency was avoided to maintain trust, friendship, and confidence among participants and the researcher. Before the administration of interviews, I asked

their permission before I recorded the IDI sessions in face-to-face and I adjusted upon their availability. Therefore, the interview schedule was set ahead of time. This is done to ensure that I would not be a reason that my participants had to be absent from their respective classes; and also, to avoid delay or cancellation of their important errands.

Beneficence emphasizes that the study should be beneficial to those who would participate in it rather than risky. It necessitates a dedication to reducing dangers to study participants rather than generating earnings owing to them. To avoid putting any participant at risk, the interviewees' identities were kept anonymous. Participants were protected at all times, and no file of information was left unattended or unsecured (Kirsh, 2019).

The researcher secured a safe location for conducting face-to-face interviews, prioritizing the safety of all participants. During the interviews, participants were provided a secure environment where they could freely share their stories without fear of rejection or criticism. To mitigate psychological risks, the information gathered during the interviews was kept confidential and secure, minimizing the potential for negative outcomes such as shame or embarrassment.

Confidentiality was also assured in this study. Upon my transcription of all of their responses, I made sure that discrete coding was used to denote each participant. This measure was grounded on the Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012 which states that any information that may potentially identify the participants in terms of their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment/location description should be carefully phrased to avoid violating participant anonymity. Hence, to address this, proper coding and other measures were applied and followed to protect the participants' identities. In conjunction, my research participants were never forced to indicate their names on any pertinent forms of this study. Another step that the researcher took was the firsthand transcription of the interviews.

Consent was also considered in the conduct of the study. As such, I made sure to respect my participants by asking them if they genuinely desired to participate in this study. Moreover, they were also encouraged to participate according to their own volition. As a testament to this, an informed assent form was signed by my participants to signify voluntary participation. This form also stipulated preliminary details about this study such as its process, methods, design, and procedures to orient the participants on what is the study all about, enabling them to make informed decisions about whether to participate or not in this inquiry. Participants who decided not to participate in the study were allowed to leave, with the assurance that their data would remain confidential even after the conduct of the study.

Justice requires a reasonable allocation of the risks and benefits as the results of the study. Therefore, I acknowledged the contribution of all the participants by giving them a token of appreciation as they became an integral part of the success of this study. I also respected their right to withdraw if they were still hesitant to share information for the study. Also, they are given due credit as a sign of gratitude for all their endeavors and efforts extended in the research.

Results and Discussion

Participants

The participants of the study were female student leaders in different public schools situated in the Municipality of Kapalong, Davao del Norte. They were all elementary female student who were serving leadership roles within their school for a school year. There were total of fourteen (14) female student leaders involved in the study.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>In-Depth Interviews (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Code</i>
Smiley	12	Female	IDI-01
Mask	12	Female	IDI-02
Curly	12	Female	IDI-03
Shy	12	Female	IDI-04
Talkative	11	Female	IDI-05
Black Lady	12	Female	IDI-06
Eyeglasses	12	Female	IDI-07
Pretty	12	Female	IDI-08
Snow	12	Female	IDI-09
Relax	12	Female	IDI-10
Friendly	12	Female	IDI-11
Tall	11	Female	IDI-12
Confident	12	Female	IDI-13
Chinita	12	Female	IDI-14
Total = 14			

The in-depth interview was conducted face-to-face inside the campus via audio recording. The researcher asked the participants if they wanted to be interviewed. The researcher gathered rich data, and both the interviewer and the interviewee were pleased by the result, resulting in a seamless flow and open communication whenever extra or probing questions were required. The participants were given

the choice to refuse to respond to any question they considered unbeneficial or in opposition to their wishes. To ensure confidentiality, the information or data collected during the interviews was treated with the utmost confidentiality. Only the researcher and the participants had access to this information, which was shared verbally but not included in the study due to its nature.

In order to adhere to the data collection process, the researcher used smartphones to record the participants' responses during the interview. Additionally, the researcher requested permission from all the participants to record the entire conversation during the interview, and they all politely agreed. All participants were accommodating and comprehended the request, except for one condition: that their identities remain anonymous in the study.

All participants were given pseudonym in order to protect their identities. For instance, Smiley was named after the participant who was always smiling during the interview, while Mask was the name given to the participant who was always wearing mask during the interview. Shy was the name given to the participant who was very shy during the interview, while Talkative was given to the participant who had talk a lot. Black Lady was the name given to the participant who wears all black during the interview.

Furthermore, Eyeglasses was given to the participant who wears cute eyeglasses while Pretty was given to the participant who had pretty face. Snow was the name given to the participant who look like snow white and Relax was given to the participant who was so relax during the interview. Friendly was the name given to the participant who has a friend beside her during the interview, while Tall was given to the participant who look tall. Confident was name given to the participant who was very confident in answering questions during the interview, and lastly Chinita was given to the participant who has really cute eyes.

Categorization of Data

After conducting in-depth interviews, the interview responses were transcribed, translated, and analyzed. The analysis commenced with the coding process, which involved organizing the materials into segments of texts to derive meaningful information. Through coding, descriptions of the participants' settings and thematic categories were generated to shape an overall depiction of the phenomenon under study. Data results were presented in the form of a table. This data gathered was handed to the data analyst for analysis of data and emerging themes.

The data was categorized into central themes based on the research questions, and these themes were presented. Thorough discussions were conducted to vividly describe the emerged themes from the study, while the core ideas of the participants' responses were also included in the table alongside the major themes.

In the data analysis, the second step by categorizing the data and presenting it in Table 2 was applied. The themes were organized according to the research questions and referred to as central themes, while the opposing significant themes were represented as co-ideas from the participants' responses. Additionally, the table included a column indicating the frequency of the responses, which served as the basis for classifying them into general, typical, and variant categories, as discussed above.

Research Question No. 1: What are the experiences of female student leaders faced in their leadership roles?

This question aimed to explore and understand the firsthand experiences of a female student in their leadership role. It sought to uncover the challenges, successes, and overall journey of these female student leaders as they navigate their leadership role in their school.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 1 were presented in Table 2. From the answers of the participants, there were five emerging themes that the researcher has found. The following themes were: encountering challenges in managing the behavior of the students, experiencing self-doubt as student leader, struggling with balancing responsibilities as a student and student-leader, engendering sense of pride to take on the role of a student- leader, and navigating different perspectives as a student- leader creates uncertainty.

Table 2. Experiences of Female Student Leaders in their Leadership Roles

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Encountering Challenges in Managing the Behavior of the Students	"Another challenge for me is the undisciplined students, they often argue or fight and it hurts my ears sometimes. So, I try to reprimand them but they really don't become disciplined." – IDI-01 "I try to stop the children from running around, I tell them not to run because they might get hurt, but sometimes, ma'am, they don't listen to me..." -IDI-02 "Some students ma'am are rude, for example they just throw garbage on the side. I scold them to not litter and keep the school clean, but they don't listen because they say I'm a female, not a male." -IDI-03 "I find it difficult, ma'am, for example, when I scold the children because they don't listen. And every time I repeatedly scold them to not litter, they still don't listen and even blaming each other." -IDI-06 "I find it difficult to handle the students because most of them don't listen when reprimanded and sometimes respond disrespectfully. It's really challenging for me to handle, I need help from other leaders because I also struggle with reprimanding." -IDI-08
Experiencing Self-Doubt as Student Leader	"I was scared and kept thinking if I can be a leader because I am a woman, right, ma'am?" -IDI-02 "I have self-doubt because I don't have an idea of how to fulfill my duties as a female leader here in our school." -IDI-07 "I have doubts about myself, thinking that maybe I won't be a good leader, and I am not very confident in

Struggling with Balancing Responsibilities as a Student and Student- Leader	<p>myself. I feel stressed because we have a lot of work to do." -IDI-09</p> <p>"As a female leader, one of my limitations is doubting myself and, at the same time, being afraid if I can uphold my leadership role here in our school." -IDI-10</p> <p>"When I was elected as president, I was really nervous because I didn't know what my responsibilities were. It was also my first time becoming a leader in SELG, so I doubted if I could continue being a leader because I was really shy, ma'am." -IDI-12</p> <p>"One of the challenges is that I find it difficult to maintain as both a student and a leader. I struggle with how to handle my responsibilities in school, ma'am." -IDI-02</p> <p>"It's like having a lot of assignments, and I can't do them because I am busy as a leader, especially when there is an event in school." -IDI-07</p> <p>"Sometimes, I am unable to fulfill my other responsibilities, ma'am, because I am busy, especially when there is a program in school. I cannot attend classes, and I am unable to participate in quizzes because I am occupied with decorating for the event, ma'am." -IDI-10</p> <p>"I find it difficult to balance my responsibilities, especially when there is a quiz in one subject and we are called for planning or we are busy preparing for an event in school." -IDI-11</p> <p>"I struggle with balancing things, especially when there is a school program and the exams are approaching. I feel a lot of pressure because I need to help decorate the area and also need to study for the exams, so it becomes difficult for me." -IDI-13</p>
Engendering Sense of Pride to take on the Role of a Student- Leader	<p>"I feel that I am brave and confident because I am included as a female leader in SELG, which can make my school better. And there are many responsibilities, ma'am, but if you just focus, you will be able to overcome your responsibilities." -IDI-01</p> <p>"I was happy because I was chosen during the time of the election, and I feel that I have a lot of responsibilities to fulfill for the school and the other students." -IDI-07</p> <p>"I am proud of myself because despite being shy, I still pursued my role as president. Being a leader in school comes with many responsibilities, but I was able to handle them, especially in disciplining enthusiastic children." -IDI-12</p>
Navigating Different Perspectives as a Student- Leader Creates Uncertainty	<p>"It's difficult to make decisions because some student leaders may have different preferences, and others may not have any, so it's hard to come to a decision." -IDI-05</p> <p>"I have doubts when making decisions because I feel undecided and afraid that I might make the wrong decision, and they might also get angry with what I have done." -IDI-09</p> <p>"One of the common limitations that I encounter is decision-making, ma'am. I struggle with making decisions on what to do, like planning ways to help the school, because I am not good in decision-making. I am afraid that my fellow leaders may not like my suggestions and may not agree." -IDI-13</p>

Encountering Challenges in Managing the Behavior of the Students

The theme focuses on the challenges that female student leaders face when it comes to managing student behavior. The participants in the study shared their experiences, highlighting a range of challenges they encounter. These challenges include dealing with undisciplined students who engage in arguments or fights, students who disregard instructions or warnings, and students who display disrespectful behavior. These challenges pose obstacles for the female student leaders in their efforts to create and maintain a disciplined and respectful learning environment. It becomes a struggle for them to effectively manage student behavior and ensure a conducive atmosphere for learning.

Based on the experiences of Smiley (pseudonym), she expresses frustration with dealing with undisciplined students who frequently engage in arguments or fights. This behavior creates a disruptive environment and has a personal impact on her. Despite her attempts to reprimand the students, she has not been successful in instilling discipline or improving their behavior. She said that:

"Challenge pud sa ako ang mga studyante nga walay disiplinado, sige sila 'g sumbagay magsakit akong dalunggan usahay. So, magtry ko 'g badlong sa ilaha pero dili jud sila madisiplina." - IDI-01

(Another challenge for me is the undisciplined students, they often argue or fight and it hurts my ears sometimes. So, I try to reprimand them but they really don't become disciplined.)

As with the other participant, Mask (pseudonyms) narrated his experience that when she attempts to prevent children from running around and warns them about the potential risk of getting hurt. However, she expresses that despite her efforts to communicate the potential consequences of running around, the children sometimes do not listen to her instructions, she shared:

"Mamadlong ko sa mga bata nga magdagan-dagan, ingnon nako sila na dili magdagan-dagan kay basig madagma sila, unya usahay ma'am dili sila maminaw sa ako,..." - IDI-02

(I try to stop the children from running around by telling them not to run because they might get hurt. However, ma'am, sometimes they just don't listen to me.)

In addition, Curly (pseudonyms) expressed the challenge she faced in managing student behavior and enforcing rules related to cleanliness. Curly (pseudonyms) highlights the specific issue of students being disrespectful by throwing garbage on the side instead of using proper disposal methods. She mentioned that she scold the students and instruct them not to litter and keep the school clean.

However, the students do not listen and disregard the instructions due to her gender. She stated that:

“Ang uban students ma’am kay badlungon! example maglabay ra silag basura sa daplin. Badlungon nako sila na dili maglabay para malimpyo ang skwelahan unya dili man sila maminaw because female daw ko dili daw ko men.” – IDI-03

(Some students can be quite disrespectful. For instance, some of them casually throw garbage on the ground. When I reprimand them and remind them to keep the school clean, they don't take me seriously, simply because I'm a woman and not a man.)

Moreover, Black Lady (pseudonym) stated that she faces difficulty in effectively scolding the children and getting them to listen to her instructions. Despite repeatedly scolding them and reminding them not to litter, the children continue to disregard her instructions and even blame each other. She stated that:

“Naglisod ko ma’am kay for example magbadlong ko sa mga bata kay dili sila maminaw, unya every time nga mag-sige ko ug badlong nga dili maglabay kay dili sila maminaw niya magtudlo-anay pa sila.” -IDI-06

(I find it difficult, ma’am, for example, when I reprimand the children because they don't listen. And every time I repeatedly reprimand them to not litter, they still don't listen and even blaming each other.)

Lastly, Pretty (pseudonym) explained that she faces difficulty in effectively reprimanding the students, as they often do not listen or respond disrespectfully. And this makes it challenging for her to handle the student. Furthermore, Pretty (pseudonyms) seeks help from other leaders, recognizing her limitations and highlighting the importance of seeking support and collaboration in managing student behavior. She mentioned that:

“Malisodan ko mag-handle sa mga student kay kasagaran sa ilaha dili maminaw pag-badlungon and usahay magtubag-tubag pa ug badlungon. Lisodan jud ko mag-handle kailangan nako’g tabang sa uban mga leaders kay maglisod jug ko’g badlong.” - IDI-08

(I find it difficult to manage the students because many of them do not listen when reprimanded, and some even respond disrespectfully. It is really challenging for me to handle on my own, and I often need support from other leaders because I also struggle with giving reprimands effectively.)

Experiencing Self-Doubt as Student Leader

The theme talks about the common experience of self-doubt and uncertainty among student leaders, particularly female leaders. The participants highlight their fears, doubts, and lack of confidence in fulfilling their leadership roles. They express the concerns about their abilities and question whether they can be effective leaders. And specifically mention self-doubt arising from being a woman, feeling unsure about fulfilling their duties, lacking confidence in themselves, and being afraid of upholding their leadership roles.

Based on Mask's (pseudonym) experience, she expressed fear and self-doubt about her ability to be a leader, specifically because of her gender. She said that:

“Nakulbaan ko na murag nagsige ko ug think kung kaya ba nako ni na maging leader kay ano diba babae man ko ma’am ba.” - IDI-02

(I was scared and kept thinking if I can be a leader because I am a woman.)

As with the other participant, Eyeglasses (pseudonym) shared her experience of feeling self-doubt, which arises from a lack of understanding or knowledge about how to fulfill her duties as a leader. She expresses uncertainty about her capabilities and may question her competence in fulfilling her role as a female leader. She stated that:

“Nagself doubt ko te kay wala man koy kalibutan kung unsaon nako pagbuhat sa’kong mga duties as female leader diria sa school namo.” - IDI-07

(I have self-doubt because I do not have an idea of how to fulfill my duties as a female leader here in our school.)

Moreover, Snow (pseudonym) expressed doubts about their own capabilities and questioned whether they would be able to fulfill the role of a good leader. This self-doubt may stem from a lack of confidence in their skills, knowledge, or experience in leadership. Snow (pseudonyms) also mentioned feeling stressed due to the workload associated with their leadership responsibilities. She mentioned that:

“Naa koy pagdoubt sa akoang sarili ato nga basig dili ko ma good leader, unya dili kaayo ko confident ato sa akoang sarili, unya mura ko’g ma-stress kay daghan kaayo me trabahoon.” - IDI-09

(I have doubts about myself, thinking that maybe I won't be a good leader, and I am not very confident in myself. I feel stressed because we have a lot of work to do.)

Furthermore, Relax (pseudonym) explained her experience, highlighting that she identifies self-doubt as a limitation she faces as a female leader. Additionally, she expresses fear and uncertainty about her ability to uphold her leadership role in the school. She said that:

“As female leader isa sa akong limitation is mag-doubt sa akoang self at the same time, mahadlok ko if kaya ba nako panindigan akoang pagkalider diria sa amoang school.”- IDI-10

(As a female leader, one of my limitations is doubting myself and, at the same time, being afraid if I can uphold my leadership role here in our school.)

Lastly, Tall (pseudonym) stated that upon being elected as the president, she experienced nervousness due to uncertainty about the specific responsibilities associated with the role. She acknowledged that it was her first time becoming a leader in SELG, which added to her apprehension. Additionally, she expressed doubt about her ability to continue being a leader because of her shyness. She stated that:

“Atong pagka-elect nako as president, nakulbaan jud ko kay wala man ko kabalo unsa akong mga responsibility and first time sad nako mahimong leader sa SELG so nag self-doubt ko kung kaya ba nako e padayon akong pagkalider kay ulawon man gud ko ma’am.”- IDI-12

(When I was elected as president, I was really nervous because I did not know what my responsibilities were. It was also my first time becoming a leader in SELG, so I doubted if I could continue being a leader because I was really shy.)

Struggling with Balancing Responsibilities as a Student and Student- Leader

The theme explores the challenges faced by female student leaders in managing their responsibilities both as students and leaders. The participants express the difficulties they encounter in finding a balance between their academic obligations and their duties as student leaders. They mention the challenges of completing assignments, attending classes, participating in quizzes, and studying for exams due to their involvement in leadership activities and events. The pressure to decorate for events or plan for programs can often conflict with their academic commitments, creating additional stress and challenges.

Based on the experience of Mask (pseudonyms), she expresses that one of the challenges that she faced is the difficulty in maintaining her responsibilities as both a student and a leader. She was struggle with how to effectively handle her responsibilities in school while also fulfilling her duties as a leader. She stated that:

“One of the challenges kay maglisod ko mag-maintain as a student and as a leader. If unsaon nako paghandle sa akong mga responsibilities sa skwelahan ma’am.”- IDI-02

(One of the challenges is that I find it difficult to maintain as both a student and a leader. I struggle with how to handle my responsibilities in school.)

As with the other participant, Eyeglasses (pseudonym) compares the situation to having a heavy workload of assignments. She expresses that she was unable to complete her assignments because she was occupied with her leadership role, particularly during school events. This inability to fulfill her academic obligations due to her leadership commitments highlights the difficulties she faces in managing her time and prioritizing tasks effectively. She shared that:

“Pareha anang daghan ug assignments unya dili nako mabuhat kay ma busy ko as leader labi na’g naay event sa school.”- IDI-07

(It's like having a lot of assignments, and I can't do them because I am busy as a leader, especially when there is an event in school.)

In addition, Relax (pseudonym) explained her experience, noting that her involvement in organizing or decorating for a program in school demands a significant amount of her time and attention. As a result, she was unable to attend classes and participate in quizzes, which are important academic responsibilities. She mentioned:

“Usahay dili ko makabuhat sakong uban responsibilities ma’am kay ma-busy ko po labi na ug naay program sa school, dili ko maka-attend ug klase then dili ko maka-apil sa quiz kay na busy man ko’g décor para sa event ma’am.”- IDI-10

(Sometimes, I am unable to fulfill my other responsibilities, because I am busy, especially when there is a program in school. I cannot attend classes, and I am unable to participate in quizzes because I am occupied with decorating for the event.)

Moreover, Friendly (pseudonym) expressed that she finds it challenging to manage her time and prioritize her commitments, especially when she has a quiz in one subject and is simultaneously called for planning or busy preparing for an event in school. The participant highlights that her leadership responsibilities, such as planning or event preparation, can sometimes conflict with her academic obligations, particularly when important assessments like quizzes are scheduled. This indicates the difficulties she faces in balancing her academic responsibilities with her leadership duties and the potential conflicts that arise as a result. She said that:

“Maglisod ko’g balance if magdungan akong mga responsibilities, pareha anang naa me quiz sa isa ka subject tapos ipatawag me ky need namo magplano or busy me para sa event na buhaton sa school.”- IDI-11

(I find it difficult to balance my responsibilities, especially when there is a quiz in one subject and we are called for planning or we are busy preparing for an event in school.)

Lastly, Confident (pseudonym) explained that she faces challenges in managing her time and priorities, particularly when there is a school program and exams are approaching simultaneously. The participant expresses feeling a significant amount of pressure because she needs to contribute to the decoration of the event area while also needing to study for her exams. The pressure to fulfill her duties as a leader while also ensuring academic success creates difficulties in finding a balance between these competing demands. She stated that:

“Maglisod ko ug balance labi na ug naay program sa skwelahan then dool na ang exam ma pressure jud ko. Kay need man nako mutabang sa pagdecorate sa area then need sad nako magstudy para sa exam so maglisod jud ko.” (IDI-13)

(I struggle with balancing things, especially when there is a school program and the exams are approaching. I feel a lot of pressure because I need to help decorate the area and also need to study for the exams, so it becomes difficult for me.)

Engendering Sense of Pride to take on the Role of a Student- Leader

The theme explores the participants' feelings of pride, confidence, and fulfillment in their positions as student leaders. They express a sense of pride and confidence in being included as female leaders in their respective Supreme Elementary Learner Government (SELG). The participants highlight their positive attitudes towards their leadership roles and their willingness to take on responsibilities for the betterment of their schools and fellow students. They also express happiness and a sense of fulfillment in being chosen as student leaders during elections. They recognize the responsibilities they have towards their schools and fellow students and are motivated to fulfill these responsibilities to the best of their abilities.

Based on the experience of Smiley (pseudonyms) expresses that she feels brave and confident because she has been given the opportunity to serve as a female leader in SELG. The participant believes that her role as a leader can contribute to making her school a better place. Despite acknowledging the numerous responsibilities that come with her leadership position, she emphasizes the importance of focusing on these responsibilities. Thus, she believes that with sufficient focus and determination, she can overcome these challenges and fulfill her duties successfully. She stated that:

“Feel nako na brave ko and confident ko kay na apil ko as female leaders sa SELG kay maka-better sa skwelahan nako. And daghan sag mga responsibility ma'am pero kung magfocus lang ka ma'am kay ma-overcome rana nimong mga responsibilities.” – IDI-01

(I feel that I am brave and confident because I am included as a female leader in SELG, which can make my school better. And there are many responsibilities, ma'am, but if you just focus, you will be able to overcome your responsibilities.)

As with other participant, Black Lady (pseudonym) expresses her happiness upon being chosen as a student leader during the election process. The participant also acknowledges the significant responsibilities that come with her role. She recognizes that she has a duty to fulfill not only for the school but also for the other students. This highlights her understanding of the importance of her role and her commitment to fulfilling her responsibilities towards the school community and her peers. She said that:

“Na happy kay napili ko tong time nga nag-election me, unya na feel nako nga daghan kog responsibility na buhaton para sa school and sa uban students.” - IDI-07

(I was happy because I was chosen during the time of the election, and I feel that I have a lot of responsibilities to fulfill for the school and the other students.)

Moreover, Confident (pseudonym) expresses pride in herself for overcoming her shyness and actively pursuing the role of president. This indicates a sense of personal growth and self-confidence in taking on a leadership position despite initial reservations. The participant acknowledges that being a leader in school entails numerous responsibilities and recognizes the weight of these responsibilities. She emphasizes her ability to handle these responsibilities effectively. In particular, she mentions her success in disciplining children, indicating her competence in maintaining discipline and guiding younger students. She mentioned that:

“Proud ko sa akoang kaugalingon kay bisan ulawon ko ge pursue japon nako ang akoang pagka president. Daghan kaayog responsibility as a leader sa school pero nakaya nako labi na ang pagbadlong sa mga bata na kiya kaayo.”-IDI-12

(I am proud of myself because despite being shy, I still pursued my role as president. Being a leader in school comes with many responsibilities, but I was able to handle them, especially in disciplining children.)

Navigating Different Perspectives as a Student- Leader Creates Uncertainty

The theme revolves around the challenges and uncertainties that student leaders face when making decisions due to the presence of diverse viewpoints among their peers. The participants expressed that they often encounter situations where different individuals have varying preferences, lack of preferences, or may not agree with their suggestions. They express doubts, fears of making the wrong decision, and concerns about potential backlash or disagreement from others. Thus, they highlight the inherent complexity of leadership roles, where student leaders must consider and navigate through multiple viewpoints and preferences.

Based on the experience of Talkative (pseudonym), she explained the difficulty she faced when trying to make decisions within a group setting. She highlighted that each individual may have their own ideas, opinions, and priorities, which can lead to conflicting

viewpoints. This diversity of preferences created uncertainty and hesitation in her decision-making process as a student leader. She struggled to find a middle ground or make a choice that could accommodate the diverse preferences of the group. She said that:

"Ano sa pag-desisyon kase baka ang ibang student leaders iba ang gusto nila at ang iba dili din, kaya ano dili din sa pagdesisyon." - IDI-05

(It's difficult to make decisions because some student leaders may have different preferences, and others may not have any, so it's hard to come to a decision.)

As with Snow (pseudonym), she expressed the presence of doubts and indecisiveness in her decision-making process. She feels uncertain and unsure about the choices she needs to make. The participant mentioned fear of making the wrong decision and the potential negative reactions from others. She is concerned that her decision might not be well-received and could lead to frustration, disappointment, or even anger from others. She stated that:

"Magduha-duha ko 'g desisyon kay mura 'g undecided kay mahadlok ko basin mali akong nabuhat nga desisyon and basin masuko pud sila sa akong gibuhat." - IDI-09

(I have doubts when making decisions because I feel undecided and afraid that I might make the wrong decision, and they might also get angry with what I have done.)

Moreover, Confident (pseudonym) explained that decision-making is a common limitation for her. She expressed her struggle in making decisions, specifically when it comes to planning ways to help the school. The participant further elaborated that her struggle with decision-making stems from a lack of confidence in her own abilities. She perceives herself as not being good at decision-making, which contributes to her hesitation and uncertainty. Additionally, Confident (pseudonyms) revealed a fear of potential negative reactions from fellow leaders. She expressed concerns that her suggestions may not be well-received or agreed upon by others. She shared that:

"Isa sa common limitation na akoang na encounter kay ang pagdesisyon jud ma'am. Maglisod ko ug desisyon kung unsay buhaton like magplano ug mga ways na makatabang sa school kay dili man gud ko hawd in terms sa pagdesisyon ma'am kay mahadlok jud ko basin dili ganahan akong mga kauban leaders sa akoang suggestion and dili sila mo agree." - IDI-13

(One of the common limitations that I encounter is decision-making, I struggle with making decisions on what to do, like planning ways to help the school, because I am not good in decision-making. I am afraid that my fellow leaders may not like my suggestions and may not agree.)

Research Question No. 2: How do female student leaders cope with the challenges as they navigate their leadership roles?

This question focused on understanding the coping mechanisms employed by female student leaders to address the challenges they encounter in their leadership roles. It explores the experiences of female student leaders and aims to uncover the strategies, approaches, and behaviors they utilize to deal with the difficulties they face. The question seeks to gain insights into how female student leaders navigate the unique challenges they encounter, such as managing diverse perspectives, making decisions, handling conflicts, and balancing responsibilities.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 2 were presented in Table 3. From the answers of the participants, 4 major themes emerged: Nurturing Patience while Dealing Challenges in a Leadership Role, Seeking Support and Guidance in Overcoming Responsibilities, Managing Academic Performance Alongside Leadership Duties, and Choosing Words Carefully to Prevent Causing Offense to Others.

Table 3. *Coping Mechanisms for the Challenges Faced by Female Student Leaders in their Leadership Roles*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Nurturing Patience while Dealing Challenges in a Leadership Role	"If I try to reprimand to them and they still don't listen, I will have to be patient in case they don't understand, and if I find out the reason why they're not listening, I can also understand what their problem is." -IDI-05
	"I am increasing my patience because they are young, ma'am, and I am older than them. So, I am just extending my patience, ma'am, if it becomes really difficult. If it's no longer manageable, I will also call other leaders to help me with the children." -IDI-06
	"The challenges have affected me in a way that it has developed my patience to handle everything." -IDI-10
	"It has affected me in a way that I have developed how to increase my patience when there are students who don't listen to me when I explain things to them." -IDI-11
Seeking Support and Guidance in Overcoming Responsibilities	"Similar to how I disciplined other highly spirited students, ma'am, then they don't listen. I will just have to be more patient with them and continue to discipline them. If they still won't listen, I will report them to the teachers, ma'am, because they are more afraid of being scolded by a teacher." -IDI-13
	"I seek advice from my family or friends who are part of the officers to help me overcome my responsibilities." -IDI-01
	"When I have a problem, I usually approach my teacher and ask for guidance. Sometimes, I also confide in my friends because I trust them since we have been together for several years." -IDI-08
	"I seek support from our SELG coordinator, ma'am, and I also handle it myself as the president." -IDI-10

Managing Academic Performance Alongside Leadership Duties	<p>"I ask for help from my team and also from our SELG coordinator so that someone can give me advice on the right actions to take in order to handle problems. Our teacher knows what needs to be done for the benefit of the school." -IDI-11</p> <p>"Most of the time, if there is a problem, I always seek help from my fellow leaders and teachers so that we can solve the problem together easily." -IDI-13</p> <p>"Even though I am a female student leader, I still balance my grades and I still have honors, even though I don't study every day. Although I participate in the SPG and study, I am still able to maintain a balance because of the support of my family and classmates. They help me figure out how to manage everything, which is why I am able to balance my studies and my involvement in SPG." -IDI-03</p> <p>"I focus on being a student and being a leader since I need it to balance because both of them are my responsibilities. If I only focus on being a student, I won't be able to fulfill my responsibilities as a leader. And if I only focus on being a leader, I won't be able to complete my projects and assignments as a student." -IDI-08</p>
Choosing Words Carefully to Prevent Causing Offense to Others.	<p>"I don't just focus on my studies, but I also fulfill my responsibilities as a leader in the SELG in school. Because what's the point of being a leader if I didn't do anything as a leader? So I strive to maintain a balance where I can maintain my grades, even though I have responsibilities as a female leader." -IDI-11</p> <p>"In order to avoid hurting or making others angry, I am careful with my words. I don't want to discourage them, instead I want to encourage them." -IDI-09</p> <p>"For me, every time I talk to other students, I am careful with my words so that they won't be hurt. Especially if I scold them because they have shown disrespect, it's a way to earn their respect as a leader." -IDI-12</p>

Nurturing Patience while Dealing Challenges in a Leadership Role

The theme of focuses on the fundamental importance of cultivating patience as a vital skill for effectively handling difficulties in a leadership position. It emphasizes the need to understand the reasons behind others' behaviors and highlights the transformative impact of challenges on the development of patience. They also highlight the importance of extending patience when working with different age groups and recognizes that nurturing patience allows them to effectively navigate difficulties, maintain discipline, and foster a positive and supportive environment for those they lead.

Talkative (pseudonym)'s statement highlights that instead of becoming frustrated or giving up, she understands the need to exercise patience. She acknowledges that the lack of understanding may be a reason for the other person's non-compliance. By remaining patient, she allows for the possibility that the person may require further explanation or support to comprehend the instructions or reprimands. Furthermore, she also highlights the importance of understanding the underlying reasons for the other person's behavior. She recognizes that by taking the time to uncover the cause behind their lack of responsiveness, she can gain insight into their problem. This understanding can help her to address the issue more effectively and find appropriate solutions. She imparted that:

"Kung mag badlong ko sa ilaha tapos hindi pa din sila nakinig aanuhin ko muna ang pasensya nako na baka hindi nila ma understood, tapos kung makita ko yung rason bakit hindi sila nakikinig ma-kuan ko din yung ano problema nila." - IDI-05

(If I try to reprimand to them and they still don't listen, I will have to be patient in case they do not understand, and if I find out the reason why they're not listening, I can also understand what their problem is.)

Furthermore, Black Lady (pseudonym) believes in exercising patience when leading young individuals. She recognizes the age difference and understands the need for patience and understanding. She is committed to extending her patience, even in challenging situations. However, she acknowledges that there may be instances when the situation becomes unmanageable, and in those cases, she is open to seeking assistance from other leaders.

She shared that:

"Ginapataas nako akong patience kay bata man ma'am then mas gulang man ko kaysa sa ila, so gina-taasan lang sad nako akong pasensya ma'am if dili na jud kaya ma'am, tawagon nalang pud nako ang uban leader's para tabangan ko sa mga bata." -IDI-06

(I am increasing my patience because they are young, ma'am, and I am older than them. So, I am just extending my patience, ma'am, if it becomes really difficult. If it's no longer manageable, I will also call other leaders to help me with the children.)

In addition, Relax (pseudonym) emphasizes the transformative impact of challenges on the development of her patience. She highlights how these experiences have shaped her ability to handle everything that comes her way. She stated that:

"Naka-apekto ang mga challenges sa akua in a way na ge-develop akoang patient para e handle ang tanan." - IDI-10

(The challenges have affected me in a way that it has developed my patience to handle everything.)

Similarly, Friendly (pseudonyms) highlighted how she overcome difficulties in leadership roles by developing the ability to increase her patience in such situations. The challenges she has faced have taught her the importance of patience and have provided her with opportunities to develop this skill. She mentioned that:

"Naka-apekto siya in a way nga na developed nako kung unsaon pagpataas sakoang pasensya kung naay mga students na dili maminaw

sa akoo kung badlungon.”-IDI-11

(It has affected me in a way that I have developed how to increase my patience when there are students who do not listen to me when I explain things to them.)

Moreover, Confident (pseudonym) expressed the need to be more patient with individuals who do not listen, recognizing that their behavior may require additional understanding and guidance. She also highlighted the importance of continuing to discipline them despite their lack of responsiveness, emphasizing the value of maintaining discipline and setting boundaries, even in challenging situations. Furthermore, she mentioned the possibility of reporting the individuals to teachers if they still do not listen, indicating her recognition of the authority and influence of teachers and the belief that the individuals may be more responsive to being scolded by a teacher. She stated that:

“Pareha anang mamadlong ko sa uban students na kiya tapos dili sila maminaw. Patas-an nalang nako akoang pasensya ma’am and badlungon na pud nako sila nya kung dili sila maminaw isumbong nalang nako sila sa mga teachers ma’am kay mas mahadlok man sila ug teacher na mo badlong sa ilaha.”-IDI-13

(Similar to how I disciplined other highly spirited students, ma’am, then they don’t listen. I will just have to be more patient with them and continue to discipline them. If they still would not listen, I will report them to the teachers, ma’am, because they are more afraid of being scolded by a teacher.)

Seeking Support and Guidance in Overcoming Responsibilities

The theme focuses on the importance of reaching out to others for assistance and advice when faced with responsibilities and challenges. It emphasizes the belief in the value of collaboration and the recognition that seeking guidance from trusted individuals can provide valuable insights and solutions. The participants highlight the strategies they employ to seek support, whether it be from family, friends, teachers, coordinators, or fellow leaders. They mention that by seeking support and guidance, individuals can tap into collective wisdom, experience, and resources, enabling them to effectively navigate their responsibilities and overcome challenges in their roles.

During the interview, Smiley (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of seeking advice from family or friends who are part of the officers to help overcome responsibilities. It highlights the value of turning to trusted individuals within one’s personal network for guidance and support in handling responsibilities. She said that:

“Mangayo ko’g advice sakong pamilya or mga friends na part sa officers para ma-overcome nako ang mga responsibilities.”-IDI-01

(I seek advice from my family or friends who are part of the officers to help me overcome my responsibilities.)

As with other participants, Pretty (pseudonym) shared her experience in seeking support and guidance to overcome challenges. She highlighted her tendency to approach her teacher and ask for guidance, recognizing the teacher’s expertise and role as a mentor. Additionally, pretty mentioned confiding in friends, emphasizing the trust built over several years of friendship. This indicates her appreciation for the perspective and support of trusted friends, who can offer different insights and emotional support. She mentioned that:

“Pag ako naa koy problema kasagaran kay sa teacher jud ko mo dool and mangutana, usahay sa akoang mga friends kay closed man kayko sa ilaha ba masaligan pud nako akoang mga friends kay pila man me ka tuig nag-uban.”- IDI-08

(When I have a problem, I usually approach my teacher and ask for guidance. Sometimes, I also confide in my friends because I trust them since we have been together for several years.)

In addition, Relax (pseudonyms) emphasized that by seeking support from the SELG coordinator, she acknowledged the importance of having guidance and assistance in dealing with a particular situation or issue, while also taking personal responsibility as the president to address and handle the situation effectively. She stated that:

“Magpatabang ko sa amoang SELG coordinator ma’am, and ginakaya nalang pud nako as president.”- IDI-10

(I seek support from our SELG coordinator, ma’am, and I also handle it myself as the president.)

Moreover, Tall (pseudonyms) expressed that to overcome her difficulty she recognizes the importance of seeking assistance and guidance from both her team members and the SELG coordinator. By involving her team, she acknowledges the collective expertise and support that can be obtained from working together. She also implies that the teacher has a deep understanding of the school’s needs and is able to provide valuable insights and guidance on the actions that should be taken to benefit the school as a whole. She said that:

“Mangayo ko’g tabang sa akong team and also sa amoang SELG coordinator kay para mas naay maka-advice sa akoo kung unsa ang tama na buhaton para mahandle nako ang mga problem since mas nakabalo man amoang teacher kung unsay dapat buhaton para maka-benefits ang school.”- IDI-11

(I ask for help from my team and also from our SELG coordinator so that someone can give me advice on the right actions to take in

order to handle problems. Our teacher knows what needs to be done for the benefit of the school.)

Lastly, Confident (pseudonyms) expressed whenever she encountered a problem, she usually seeks help from her fellow leaders and teachers. She believes that by working together with these individuals, they can easily find solutions to the problem at hand. The participant values the collective knowledge, experience, and expertise of their peers and recognizes that collaborating with them can lead to more efficient and effective problem-solving. She mentioned that:

“Most of the time if naay problema mangayo jud ko ug tabang sa akoang mga kauban leaders and sa teachers aron dal ira ma solve ang problema.”-IDI-13

(Most of the time, if there is a problem, I always seek help from my fellow leaders and teachers so that we can solve the problem together easily.)

Managing Academic Performance Alongside Leadership Duties

The theme focuses on the importance of managing academic performance alongside leadership duties. The participants mentioned that they need to balance their roles as students and leaders. They emphasize that focusing solely on one aspect, either being a student or being a leader, would result in neglecting the responsibilities of the other role. It requires finding a balance, seeking support from others, and actively fulfilling responsibilities in both roles.

During the interview, Curly (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of determination to excel both academically and as a student leader. It showcases her ability to find a balance between these two roles, despite not dedicating every day to studying. Her success in maintaining good grades and receiving honors demonstrates the effectiveness of her approach. She also mentioned that the support from her family and classmates plays a crucial role in helping her to navigate her commitments and find strategies to effectively manage her time and responsibilities. She stated that:

“Even though I am a female student leader, I still balance my grade and I’m still with honors, even though I’m not doing my studies everyday. Though naga SPG ko and study but na balance japon nako tungod sa tabang sakong family, sakong mga classmates. Tabangan ko nila kung unsaon to...maong na balance nako akong study ug pag SPG.”-IDI-03

(Even though I am a female student leader, I still balance my grades and I still have honors, even though I do not study every day. Although I participate in the SPG and study, I am still able to maintain a balance because of the support of my family and classmates. They help me figure out how to manage everything, which is why I am able to balance my studies and my involvement in SPG.)

As with other participant, Pretty (pseudonyms) emphasizes the importance of balancing her roles as a student and a leader. She understands that neglecting one role while focusing solely on the other can lead to failures and compromises. By striving for balance, she can effectively fulfill both roles and meet her obligations without sacrificing one for the other. She stated that:

“Nag-focus ko sa akong pagka-studyante ug akong pagkalider kay kailangan man nako na e balance kay both of them is my responsibility. Kay if magfocus lang ko sa akoang pagka student dili man nako mabuhat ang responsibility nako as leader, then if magfocus rasad ko sa akoang pagkalider dili sad nako mabuhat akong mga projects, assignments as students.”-IDI-08

(I focus on being a student and being a leader since I need it to balance because both of them are my responsibilities. If I only focus on being a student, I won't be able to fulfill my responsibilities as a leader. And if I only focus on being a leader, I won't be able to complete my projects and assignments as a student.)

Similarly, Friendly (pseudonyms) expressed the importance of balancing her academic studies and her responsibilities as a leader in the SELG (Student Executive Leadership Group) at school. She believes that being a leader is not just a title, but it requires taking action and fulfilling responsibilities. Therefore, she strives to maintain a balance where she can excel academically while also fulfilling her duties as a female leader. By finding this balance, she can effectively manage both aspects of her life and make a meaningful impact in her leadership role. She mentioned that:

“Dili lang ko magfocus sa akoang pag-skwela but ginabuhat sad nako akoang mga responsibilities as leader sa SELG sa school. Kay unsa may pulos nako na pagkalider if magpakahoy-kahoy rako sa school na leader man ko, so ge balance lang nako na ma-maintain pud akoang mga grades bisan naa koy responsibilities as female leader.”- IDI-11

(I don't just focus on my studies, but I also fulfill my responsibilities as a leader in the SELG in school. Because what's the point of being a leader if I didn't do anything as a leader? So, I strive to maintain a balance where I can maintain my grades, even though I have responsibilities as a female leader.)

Choosing Words Carefully to Prevent Causing Offense to Others.

The theme focuses on the importance of choosing words carefully to prevent offense to others. The participants acknowledge that the words they use have the power to impact others emotionally and can either build or damage relationships. By choosing their words carefully, they aim to create an environment of respect, empathy, and understanding. They encourage thinking before speaking and considering the perspectives and sensitivities of those they are communicating with. They also emphasize the importance of considering

the emotional well-being of others and striving to maintain positive and harmonious interactions.

During the interview, Relax emphasized the importance of being cautious with her words to prevent causing harm or anger to others. She aims to avoid discouraging others and instead wants to provide encouragement. She imparted that:

“Para walay malain or masuko sa akong maging careful ko sa akong mga words, dili nako sila e discouraged instead e encouraged nako sila..”-IDI-09

(In order to avoid hurting or making others angry, I am careful with my words. I do not want to discourage them, instead I want to encourage them.)

As with other participant, Tall (pseudonyms) explained the importance of being careful with her words when interacting with other students to prevent causing hurt. She particularly emphasized the need for caution when scolding students who have shown disrespect, as it is seen as a way to earn their respect as a leader. She said that:

“Para sa akong every time makig-storya ko sa uban students maging careful ko sa akong mga words para dili gud sila malain, specially if badlungon nako sila kay subra na ilang kasipat in that way man gud hatagan or taas ilang respeto sa imoha as leader.”- IDI-12

(For me, every time I talk to other students, I am careful with my words so that they won't be hurt. Especially if I scold them because they have shown disrespect, it's a way to earn their respect as a leader.)

Research Question No. 3: What are the insights of female student leaders that they can share to inspire and empower other young women to pursue leadership roles?

This research question focuses on understanding the perspectives and experiences of female student leaders. It aims to gather insights and knowledge from these leaders to inspire and empower other young women aspiring to take on leadership roles. The question explores the unique perspectives, lessons learned, successes, challenges, and strategies of female student leaders. By understanding their insights, the research aims to identify key factors that can motivate and empower other young women to pursue leadership positions.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 2 were presented in Table 3. From the answers of the participants, 5 major themes emerged: demonstrate complete accounting in leadership duties, exude unwavering strength and confidence, enhanced leadership and communication skills, demonstrate fervent passion and commitment in leadership, and empowerment and breaking of gender stereotypes in leadership.

Table 4. Insights from Female Student Leaders that Will Inspire Young Women to take on Leadership Roles

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Demonstrate Complete Accounting in Leadership Duties	"Be responsible for your work, you should not act worthless. You should know what your tasks are and work hard on the tasks assigned by the school." -IDI-02 "What I have learned, ma'am, is that not everyone will appreciate everything, including your wants or opinions. Also, I have learned as a leader that you have to be responsible." -IDI-06 "Be responsible, and always accept the challenge. Make simple but significant things, and take it easy like just calm." -IDI-07 "My advice to other women who aspire to become female leaders is that they should be responsible. They should know how to handle any situation and they should know how to fulfill their responsibilities as a leader." -IDI-08 "Be responsible and do your best so that you will become a good leader in your school." -IDI-14
Exude Unwavering Strength and Confidence	"What I tell them is to be strong and not to fall into negativity... They should focus on the positive. As a leader, you should be confident." -IDI-02 "So, for people who aspire to become SELG leaders, my advice to them is to be strong and have confidence." -IDI-03 "Be strong in your feelings, so that whatever is in your heart or what you desire, you won't easily surrender." -IDI-06 "Be strong and don't give up easily. Stand firm in your position because it's also for your own improvement." -IDI-11 "My message to female students who want to become a leaders in school is that you should have high confidence. If you have confidence, you will be able to handle challenges and effectively communicate with other students." -IDI-12
Enhanced Leadership and Communication Skills	"I have also enhanced my communication skills and leadership skills by learning how to handle situations where I need to take a stand as a leader, not just within the school but also outside of it." -IDI-08 "My leadership skills were boosted ma'am by learning how to handle students to become good students, as well as how to contribute for the school improvement, even in small ways." -IDI-10 "For me, leadership skills and communication skills, because of this position, I become a responsible leader who can be approached by everyone. And I know how to listen to the voices of other students, and because of this position my communication skills has enhanced and allowed me to build good relationships with other students." -IDI-11

Demonstrate Fervent Passion and Commitment in Leadership	"You should not be shy and you should have the passion to lead so that you won't back out." -IDI-10
Empowerment and Breaking of Gender Stereotypes In Leadership	"What I have learned is that you should have the passion to lead and you should not be afraid to fulfill your responsibilities in order to become a good leader in your school." -IDI-12
	"My self-confidence has been boosted even though I am a woman. Just because I am a woman doesn't mean I can't do what male leaders can do." -IDI-08
	"Since I am very shy, my leadership role in school is a great opportunity for me to boost my confidence. This newfound confidence can be used in various aspects of my life. And because of this, I am pursuing other opportunities, knowing that being a woman does not limit my ability to become a leader. I believe, ma'am, that gender does not determine leadership. If it is what you truly desire in your heart, you should pursue it with confidence." -IDI-14

Demonstrate Complete Accounting in Leadership Duties

The theme emphasized the importance of demonstrating complete accountability in leadership duties. The participants consistently emphasize the need to be responsible, fulfill assigned tasks, and handle various situations effectively. They highlight the significance of taking ownership, accepting challenges, and striving to do one's best as a leader. This underscores the idea that accountability is crucial for effective leadership and encourages aspiring leaders to prioritize responsibility and fulfill their duties diligently. By demonstrating complete accountability, leaders can inspire trust, foster positive relationships, and effectively lead their teams or organizations.

During the interview, Mask (pseudonyms) emphasizes the importance of being responsible in leadership roles. She asserted that individuals should take responsibility for their work and avoid acting in a manner that undermines their worth. Additionally, she highlights the significance of knowing one's tasks and working diligently on the tasks assigned by the school. She stated that:

"Be responsible to your works, dapat dili ka magpakahoy-kahoy, dapat e kuan nimo unsa imong task, unya kung unsay mga kuan sa school e work hard jud nimo." -IDI-02

(Be responsible for your work, you should not act worthless. You should know what your tasks are and work hard on the tasks assigned by the school.)

Similarly, Black Lady (pseudonyms) reflects on her learning experience and acknowledges that not everyone will appreciate her wants or opinions. She emphasizes the importance of being responsible as a leader. This highlights the understanding that not everyone will agree with or appreciate her perspectives, underscoring the significance of taking responsibility in a leadership role. She said that:

"Akong nakat-unan ma'am kay dili tanan bagay or gusto, or opinion nimo is ma appreciate sa uban ma'am. And nakat-unan pun nako as a leader kay be responsible jud ma'am." - IDI-06

(What I have learned, ma'am, is that not everyone will appreciate everything, including your wants or opinions. Alos, I have learned as a leader that you have to be responsible.)

In addition, Eyeglasses (pseudonyms) emphasizes the importance of responsibility and accepting challenges in leadership roles. She encourages making simple but significant contributions and maintaining a calm demeanor. This statement highlights the importance of being accountable, embracing challenges, contributing meaningfully, and maintaining composure in leadership roles. She mentioned that:

"Be responsible, unya accept the challenge always. And make it simple but significant things, and take it easy like magkalma lang sila." - IDI-07

(Be responsible, and always accept the challenge. Make simple but significant things, and take it easy like just calm.)

Moreover, Pretty (pseudonyms) advises other women aspiring to become leaders to be responsible. She emphasizes the importance of knowing how to handle any situation that may arise in a leadership role. Additionally, she stresses the need for these aspiring leaders to understand how to fulfill their responsibilities effectively. This advice underscores the importance of accountability, adaptability, and understanding of one's duties in a leadership position. She said that:

"Ang akoang matambag sa uban babae nga gusto mahimong female leaders kay dapat be responsible dapat kahibalo sila maghandle sa bisan unsa nga situation ug kabalo sila mo buhat sa ilang mga responsibilities as a leader." -IDI-08

(My advice to other women who aspire to become female leaders is that they should be responsible. They should know how to handle any situation and they should know how to fulfill their responsibilities as a leader.)

Lastly, Chinita (pseudonyms) encourages individuals aspiring to be good leaders in their school to prioritize responsibility and give their best effort. By embodying these qualities, leaders can effectively guide and inspire others, fostering a positive and impactful leadership presence. She stated that:

"Be responsible, buhata imohang best para mahimo ka na good leader sa inyohang skwelahan." -IDI-14

(Be responsible and do your best so that you will become a good leader in your school.)

Exude Unwavering Strength and Confidence

The theme emphasizes the importance of exuding unwavering strength and confidence in leadership roles. The participants consistently highlight the significance of emotional and mental strength, avoiding negativity, and focusing on the positive. It encourages aspiring leaders to cultivate confidence in their abilities and beliefs. By exuding strength and confidence, leaders can effectively handle challenges, communicate, and inspire others.

During the interview, Mask (pseudonyms) emphasizes the importance of being strong and avoiding negativity. The participant advises others to focus on the positive aspects instead. She also highlights that as a leader, it is essential to be confident. This statement underscores the significance of maintaining a positive mindset, resilience, and self-assurance in leadership roles. It suggests that by staying strong and focusing on the positive, leaders can effectively navigate challenges and inspire others. She stated that:

“Ang iingon nako sa ila nga maging strong, unya dapat dili ka ma fell sa negative...dapat magkuan ra jud ka sa positive... Dapat maging confident ka as a leader.”- IDI-02

(What I tell them is to be strong and not to fall into negativity. They should focus on the positive. As a leader, you should be confident.)

As with other participant, Curly (pseudonyms) advises individuals aspiring to become SELG leaders to be strong and have confidence. She emphasizes that by embodying these qualities, aspiring leaders can effectively navigate challenges, inspire others, and fulfill their leadership roles successfully. This advice highlights the importance of inner strength and self-assurance in leadership positions. She said that:

“So, sa people na ganahan kaayo mahimong SELG leader, ang akua lang ma advice sa ila is to be strong, and to have confidence.”- IDI-03

(So, for people who aspire to become SELG leaders, my advice to them is to be strong and have confidence.)

In addition, Black Lady (pseudonyms) advises individuals to be strong in their feelings and not easily surrender to challenges or give up on their desires. She highlights the importance of emotional strength and resilience in pursuing passions and goals. By cultivating this inner strength, individuals can persevere through difficulties and maintain the determination to achieve what is in their hearts or what they desire. She imparted that:

“Be strong sa imohang feelings para kung unsa ang na asa imohang dughan or gusto nimo dili dayon ka mo surrender.”-IDI-06

(Be strong in your feelings, so that whatever is in your heart or what you desire, you won't easily surrender.)

Moreover, Friendly (pseudonyms) advises individuals to be strong, not giving up easily and standing firm in their position for personal growth and improvement. This highlights the significance of resilience and perseverance in pursuing goals, emphasizing that challenges should not hinder individuals from pursuing their aspirations. She stated that:

“Be strong, and dili dapat ka mo give up ug dali. Panindigi kung unsay position nimo kay para rasad na sa imohang improvement.”- IDI-11

(Be strong and do not give up easily. Stand firm in your position because it's also for your own improvement.)

Lastly, Tall (pseudonyms) advises aspiring female student leaders to have high confidence, emphasizing its importance in effectively handling challenges and communicating with others. This highlights the role of confidence in leadership, enabling individuals to navigate obstacles and foster effective communication in the school environment. She mentioned that:

“Akoang message sa mga female student na gusto mahimong leader sa school is dapat taas ka ug confident. Kay ug naa kay confident kaya nimo mo handle sa mga challenges and magamit pud nimo na sa pag communicate sa uban students.” -IDI-12

(My message to female students who want to become a leader in school is that you should have high confidence. If you have confidence, you will be able to handle challenges and effectively communicate with other students.)

Enhanced Leadership and Communication Skills

The theme emphasized the importance of developing both leadership and communication skills in order to be effective leaders. It highlights the value of taking a stand, contributing to the school's improvement, and building positive relationships with others. By enhancing these skills, individuals can become more capable leaders who can effectively lead, communicate, and foster positive change within their school community.

During the interview, Pretty (pseudonyms) shared her insight about her experience in leadership, highlighting the enhancement of her communication and leadership skills. She mentions that she has learned how to handle situations where she needs to take a stand as a leader, both within and outside of the school. This suggests that through her leadership role, she has gained valuable experience in effectively communicating her ideas and making decisions confidently. By learning to navigate challenging situations, she has further

developed her leadership abilities. She said that:

“And also na enhance pud akoang communication skills and leadership skills kung unsaon paghandle sa isa ka butang na mo stand ka as leader dili lang sa school but outside of school pud.”-IDI-08

(I have also enhanced my communication skills and leadership skills by learning how to handle situations where I need to take a stand as a leader, not just within the school but also outside of it.)

As with other participant, Relax (pseudonyms) shares an insight about her experience in leadership. She mentions that her leadership skills were boosted by learning how to handle students and guide them to become good students. Additionally, she highlights the importance of contributing to school improvement, even in small ways. This insight emphasizes the value of being able to effectively handle and guide students, as well as the significance of making contributions, no matter how small, towards the betterment of the school. She stated that:

“Na boost akoang leadership skills ma’am kung unsaon paghandle sa mga students para mahimong good student and kung unsaon pagtabang sa school para naay improvement bisan sa gamay lang na way po.”-IDI-10

(My leadership skills were boosted by learning how to handle students to become good students, as well as how to contribute for the school improvement, even in small ways.)

Similarly, Friendly (pseudonyms) shares her experience in leadership, highlighting the development of her leadership and communication skills. She mentions that holding a leadership position has made her a responsible leader who can be approached by everyone. She also emphasizes her ability to listen to the voices of other students, which has enhanced her communication skills and allowed her to build good relationships with her peers. She mentioned that:

“Para sa akong leadership skill and communication skills, kay tungod ani na position nahimo kung responsible leader na pwedeng madoolan sa tanan, and kbalu maminaw sa voices sa uban students and also tungod sa akong position na enhanced akoang communication skills and nakabuild ko ug good relationship sa uban students.”-IDI-11

(For me, leadership skills and communication skills, because of this position, I become a responsible leader who can be approached by everyone. And I know how to listen to the voices of other students, and because of this position my communication skills has enhanced and allowed me to build good relationships with other students.)

Demonstrate Fervent Passion and Commitment in Leadership

The theme explores the importance of demonstrating fervent passion and commitment in leadership roles. The participants consistently emphasize the need to have a strong passion for leadership and not be afraid to fulfill responsibilities. They highlight the significance of being enthusiastic, dedicated, and committed to effectively lead in their school.

This highlight the idea that successful leaders are those who possess a genuine passion for their role and are willing to put in the necessary effort and dedication. By demonstrating fervent passion and commitment, individuals can inspire others, overcome challenges, and make a positive impact in their school community.

During the interview, Relax (pseudonyms) encourages individuals to overcome shyness and cultivate a passion for leadership. She suggests that being shy can hinder individuals from fully embracing their leadership potential. By having the passion to lead, individuals are more likely to stay committed and not back out from their responsibilities. She stated that:

“Like dili mag ulaw-ulaw po and dapat naa kay passion mo lead para dili mag back-out back-out.”-IDI-10

(You should not be shy and you should have the passion to lead so that you won't back out.)

Similarly, Tall (pseudonyms) emphasized the importance of having a passion for leadership and not being afraid to fulfill responsibilities. This insight suggests that a strong passion for leading and a willingness to take on responsibilities are essential for becoming a good leader in school. By demonstrating passion and fearlessness, individuals can effectively fulfill their duties and make a positive impact in their leadership roles. She said that:

“Ang na learn nako is dapat naa kay passion mo lead and dili dapat ka mahadlok mo buhat sa imohang mga responsibility para mahimo kang good leader sa inyohang skwelahan.”-IDI-12

(What I have learned is that you should have the passion to lead and you should not be afraid to fulfill your responsibilities in order to become a good leader in your school.)

Empowerment and Breaking of Gender Stereotypes In Leadership

The theme focuses on the empowerment of individuals and breaking gender stereotypes in leadership roles. The participants emphasize the importance of self-confidence and reject the notion that being a woman limits their leadership abilities. They encourage individuals to pursue leadership roles with confidence and determination, highlighting that gender should not determine one's potential.

During the interview, Pretty (pseudonyms) shared that her self-confidence has been boosted despite being a woman. She emphasizes that being a woman does not limit her ability to do what male leaders can do. This insight highlights the importance of self-confidence and challenges the notion that gender should determine one's capabilities in leadership. Her statement promotes empowerment and equality, emphasizing that women can excel and achieve success in leadership roles, just like their male counterparts. She said that:

“Na boost akoang self-confidence even though babae ko like dili porket babae ko dili na nako pwede nga mabuhat ang mabuhat sa male nga leaders.” -IDI-08

(My self-confidence has been boosted even though I am a woman. Just because I am a woman does not mean I cannot do what male leaders can do.)

Similarly, Chinita (pseudonyms) shared her insight on the impact of her leadership role in school. She mentions that her shy nature has made her leadership role a valuable opportunity to boost her confidence. This newfound confidence has had a positive influence on various aspects of her life. As a result, she is pursuing other opportunities, recognizing that being a woman does not limit her ability to become a leader. Chinita firmly believed that gender should not determine leadership and encourages individuals to pursue their desires with confidence. This insight highlights the transformative power of leadership in boosting confidence and breaking gender stereotypes. She stated that:

“Since ulawon man kaayo ko, akong pagkalider sa skwelahan is dako kaayo na opportunity para ma boost nako akoang confidence. And kani na confident is magamit nako sa lahi-lahi na aspect sa akoang life. Ug tungod pud ani is ma pursue nako ang uban opportunity like dili porket babae ko dili nako pwede nga mahimong leader. I believe ma’am wala na sa gender ang leadership, kay if mao na imong gusto sa imohang heart dapat sundon nimo with confident.” -IDI-14

(Since I am very shy, my leadership role in school is a great opportunity for me to boost my confidence. This newfound confidence can be used in various aspects of my life. And because of this, I am pursuing other opportunities, knowing that being a woman does not limit my ability to become a leader. I believe, ma'am, that gender does not determine leadership. If it is what you truly desire in your heart, you should pursue it with confidence.)

Conclusions

The journey of exploring the experiences of female student leaders has been both enlightening and rewarding. Through this study, I have uncovered valuable insights into the challenges, aspirations, and strengths of these young leaders, shedding light on the importance of empowerment, support, and inclusivity in leadership development. As I reflect on my research journey, I am reminded of the resilience and determination demonstrated by the participants, who navigate complex societal expectations and stereotypes with grace and courage. Their stories serve as a testament to the transformative power of leadership and the potential for positive change when individuals are empowered to embrace their full potential.

Moreover, it is clear that there is still much work to be done in promoting gender equity and empowerment in leadership roles. By amplifying the voices of female student leaders and advocating for inclusive policies and practices, we can create a more just and equitable society where all individuals have the opportunity to thrive and succeed. As researchers, educators, and community leaders, it is our collective responsibility to champion the rights and aspirations of female leaders, ensuring that they are supported, valued, and empowered to make meaningful contributions to their schools, communities, and society at large.

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